

DEVELOPMENT OF BIODEGRADABLE BANDAGES FROM PINUS SYLVESTRIS BARK: PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Relevance. Modern medicine has an urgent need for environmentally friendly, biocompatible, and effective wound dressing materials. The bark of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) is a promising renewable source of biologically active compounds with proven antimicrobial and wound-healing properties, which determines the relevance of its study.

Objective of the study: To substantiate the possibility of using *Pinus sylvestris* bark for the development of environmentally friendly wound dressing materials with enhanced antiseptic properties.

Materials and Methods: A phytochemical analysis of the bark was carried out using IR spectrophotometry and thin-layer chromatography. A technology for processing the bark into fibrous material was developed, including the stages of cleaning, fiberization, and stabilization. The antimicrobial activity and resistance to biodegradation were evaluated under incubation conditions with fungal cultures *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The physico-mechanical properties of the obtained samples (tensile strength, moisture absorption, air permeability) were also studied.

Results: It was found that pine bark is rich in flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol), phenolic acids (caffeic, ferulic), and terpenoids (α -pinene), which account for its strong antioxidant and antiseptic activity. The developed bandages demonstrated superior characteristics compared to synthetic and gauze analogues: tensile strength — 45 N, moisture absorption — 180%, air permeability — 2.5 cm³/cm²/s. A biodegradation resistance experiment showed that impregnation with yarrow extract significantly increased the material's resistance to fungal destruction (affected area of only 15% versus 40% in the untreated sample and 70% in the synthetic sample on day 14).

Conclusions: The results of the study confirm the potential of Scots pine bark for the production of biodegradable, biocompatible wound dressing materials with prolonged antiseptic activity. Further research will focus on optimizing the technology and conducting preclinical trials.